

PARENTS INVOLVEMENT IN READING AT HOME OF GRADE 1 PUPILS: INPUT FOR A PROPOSED TRAINING

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Parents Involvement in Reading at Home of Grade 1 Pupils: Input for a Proposed Training

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Abstract

The descriptive correlational research design was used in this study. The profile of parent-respondents surveyed, encompassing age, educational attainment, occupation, and family income, provides crucial insights into parental involvement dynamics in children's reading development. Across age groups, notably 36-45, parents play pivotal roles through shared reading and access to materials. While older parents may favor traditional practices, parental modeling remains vital. Occupation and income impact engagement, urging targeted support for socioeconomically constrained families. Emphasizing a supportive home literacy environment is essential for enhancing literacy and academic achievement. Additionally, Grade 1 pupils' performance in the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) underscores parental involvement's critical role. High correlations between parental guidance and children's phonemic awareness and decoding skills highlight the positive impact of regular reading. Home access to reading materials strongly correlates with reading performance, emphasizing print-rich environments' importance. Promoting parental involvement and access to reading materials enhances educational experiences and achievements for young learners. Understanding and addressing factors influencing parental involvement can foster effective collaboration among educators, policymakers, and parents to create supportive environments nurturing children's literacy skills and academic success.

Keywords: *early grade reading assessment, parents involvement, reading, literary skills*

Introduction

The key objective of early education is to help children in learning to read (Wigfield, Gladstone, & Turci, 2016). Moreover, the gained skills from primary reading instruction have a significant effect on the future reading and writing performance of these children and their academic achievements (Değirmenci Gündoğmuş, 2018). Proficiency in reading is essential for academic success after the third grade. As students move to a higher level, the amount of reading also increases. Children's ability to read becomes useful in later literacy skills, facilitating social interaction between adults and children, as well as encouraging children to be involved with the world around them is considered beneficial for children growing up in challenging circumstances (Collier, 2019). A lack of reading proficiency can lead students to struggle and fall behind as more complex concepts begin to arise (Ellen, 2019). Therefore, conducting high-quality primary-level reading programs is significant to ensure and improve both reading fluency and reading comprehension for children because these skills are essential at this stage of development.

The Department of Education (DepEd) issued a program called Every Child a Reader program (ECARP). This program aims to develop the literacy and numeracy skills of every Filipino learner from Kindergarten to Grade 3 (DepEd, 2017). It is designed to equip elementary school students with strategic reading and writing skills to become independent young readers and writers (Magaso, 2021).

Educators are required to prepare for the implementation of mandatory reading programs in school systems. In addition, teachers can also use a method called parent-supported reading that can be useful to any reading program (Howell, 2008). The approach is a reading strategy in which parents are encouraged to help their kid read with the help of an adviser (Anthony & Plete, 2021).

Parents' involvement in children's education is generally positively associated with children's learning and adjustment (Kim & Sheridan, 2015). Family involvement in elementary school can support children's academic achievement and offset educational risk often associated with low socioeconomic status (Boonk et al., 2018), leading to calls for urgent efforts to engage families in their children's education (McWayne, 2015). Randomized control trials are needed to examine program effects on engaging family involvement (Garbacz et al., 2017).

According to Keleş & Doğan (2021), parent-assisted reading intervention programs have been effective in improving students' reading fluency and comprehension. Additionally, Family literacy activities have been found to have a significant impact on children's literacy learning. These activities include reading aloud, reading together, and providing printed materials. (Huag & Doleis, 2007). If parents are familiar with literacy, they can use phonetics, contextual cues, picture cues, and other word recognition skills to help their children (Mcmahon, 2010).

Numerous academicians argue why Philippines, considered as one of the best-speaking countries globally, ranks lowest in the survey in terms of education specifically in reading proficiency (Caraig & Quimbo, 2022). Hence, teachers in different schools in our country always seek an immediate action since they already considered problems such as the low performance of their students in terms of reading comprehension (Gatcho & Futierrez, 2020). As supported by Balinas et. Al, (2017), there are millions of Filipino who have limited literacy skills in which they revealed that there are kindergarten students in the remote areas of Mindanao who have continuous poor reading performances. On the other hand, if this issues will continuously occur and happen, then our country might be called as "a nation of non-readers" that will be a serious problem of the Philippines in the future that will arise (Luz, 2007).

In despite of the urgency of the government in implementing programs and interventions that prioritize the improvement in reading performances of the students, the researcher observes that the learners in primary level of Casiguran, Aurora most especially in the respondents' schools of Casiguran Central School, Tinib-Calangcuasan Integrated School and Dibacong Elementary School are still struggling to meet the minimum required proficiency in reading. From the baseline data gathered by the researcher Casiguran CS has 34 non-readers, Dibacong has 21 and TCIS has 20. It seems like there are other factor that affects these learners to maximize their ability in reading performances. Furthermore, due to the fact that parents has the greatest influence to their children such as the way they support them as well as their involvement in school programs for their children, this study hypothesized that parent's involvement in reading has a relationship to the reading proficiency of their children. In this regard, the researcher would like to know the factors affecting the parents' involvement in Reading at home, particularly in Grade 1 to improve the reading performance of their children.

Research Questions

This study determined the factors affecting the Parents Involvement in Reading at home of Grade 1 pupils: Input for a Proposed Training during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of parent-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. educational attainment;
 - 1.3. occupation; and
 - 1.4. monthly income?
2. What is the level of performance of the Grade 1 pupils in Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) on the following reading components:
 - 2.1. book and print knowledge;
 - 2.2. phonemic awareness;
 - 2.3. alphabetic knowledge; and
 - 2.4. decoding skills?
3. What are the parents' involvement in Reading at Home of Grade 1 in terms of:
 - 3.1. knowledge about beginning reading;
 - 3.2. time allotment for parental guidance in reading; and
 - 3.3. availability of reading materials at home?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of performance of grade 1 pupils and the factors affecting parent involvement in reading at home?
5. What program can be proposed to improve the parents' involvement of Grade 1 pupils?

Methodology

Research Design

To achieve the goals of this study, descriptive-correlation method was used in gathering data. According to USC Libraries (2023), quantitative methods emphasize the objective measurement and statistical, mathematical or numerical analysis of data collected through surveys, questionnaires and surveys, or by using computational methods to manipulate existing statistics. The main goal of quantitative research is to generate knowledge and create an understanding of the members of society. It relates to a specific group of people to be sampled (Allen, 2017).

The descriptive correlational research design was used in this study through a survey method with a questionnaire checklist as a research instrument. Descriptive research was used to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the school heads be described in terms. Person r correlation is a statistical measure used to establish the direction and strength of the relationship between two variables.

The researcher used correlational design which measure and evaluate variables involved in the study. Additionally, this study design aims to explore whether there is a relationship between the two variables (Grand Canyon University, 2021).

Quantitative data analysis aims to reveal underlying patterns, trends, and relationships in any of a research (Albers, 2017).

The participants of this study were the parents of the grade 1 pupils among the public elementary schools in the District of Casiguran.

Respondents

The sampling method used in the study is a non-probability sampling where the decisions upon the individuals involved in the study are taken by the researcher based on certain criteria that are inclined to the research issue or the willingness of individuals to participate (Rai & Thapa, 2015). The study used purposive sampling method which aims to capture the best sample that are match with the main objective of the research (Campbell et al., 2020).

The respondents of this study are from different elementary schools in Casiguran, Aurora, these are the grade 1 student parents of slow learners. As assessed, there are total of 224 students from 3 schools, for which 75 pupils were confirmed to be slow learners based from

the results of pre-assessment and post-assessment of EGRA.

Table 1. Population of the Study

<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Total No. Learners</i>	<i>No. of Parents Involve in the Study</i>
1. CCS	137	34
2. Tinib/Calanguasan TCIS	32	18
3. Dibacong ES	55	20
Total:	224	72

Instruments

The researcher adapted research questions that served as the source of data for the study. The questionnaire has three (3) parts. The first part contains the description of the profile of the parents-respondents in terms of age, educational attainment, occupation, and monthly income. The second part is about the factor affecting the parents' involvement in Reading Program in Grade 1 in terms of knowledge about beginning reading, time allotment for parental guidance in reading, and availability of reading materials. Part II of the questionnaire items have a Filipino translation to facilitate honest response of the respondents. And the last part is the open-ended question.

According to Zulueta (2010), questionnaires such as research instrument, require the respondents to neither write answers to questions about the topic or answer orally. The answer form is usually structures. There are fixed choices or the form may be open. The respondents can create their own words. The key word in questionnaire construction is relevance which has three facets: relevance of the study's goal, relevance of questions to the goals of the study and relevance of the question to the questions to the individual.

Finally, all the data were gathered using different parts of the instrument were collected, tabulated, analysed, and interpreted.

Procedure

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of Aurora to express the intention to conduct the said study who in return will endorse to the SDO Sub-office of Casiguran District for the Public Schools District Supervisor and for the school heads. The data collection process began.

A questionnaire was forwarded to the respondents to observe the minimum health standards and protocols. As a standard procedure in giving questionnaires, the purpose and possible benefits of the study were explained to the respondents. The confidentiality of information was assured by the researcher. With the researcher personally handling the administration of the survey questionnaires, a one hundred percent (100%) retrieval rate will be achieved.

To encourage honest response, even in sensitive issues, confidentiality of respondents will be assured to the respondents. Once everything is settled, the survey questionnaires will be administered systematically to all respondents. The questionnaires were retrieved by the researcher and data were organized, coded, tallied, analysed, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

The data were tallied, organized and tabulated in the Excel Spreadsheet.

To answer the specific questions, the data derived from the research instrument were gathered the profile of the respondents and degree of utilization of educators' teaching tools that were used in the treatment of the data gathered are the following:

For question number 1, the parent-respondents were profiled based on their age, educational attainment, occupation, and monthly income. The responses were analyzed and interpreted using frequency count and percentage.

For question number 2, which contained frequency count and percentage were used.

For question number 3, factors affecting the parents' involvement in Reading Program in terms of knowledge about beginning reading, time allotment for parental guidance in reading, and availability of reading materials at home. Each statement on the questionnaire was based on a Likert scale, and each answer was assigned weights to establish normally distributed scores.

For the question number 4, the Pearson R Correlation was used to test the significant relationship. All data was transcribed by the statistician as well as the computations for the said statistics.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher applied the principles of ethical considerations developed by Bryman and Bell (2007). With regards to the involvement to this study, the participants were subjected to harm in any ways. Prior to the study, full consent was obtained from the participants, the parents among the Public Elementary Schools in the District of Casiguran. In addition, the protection of the privacy of research participants will be ensured. Voluntary participation of respondents in the research treated very important. Moreover, they have rights to withdraw from the study at any stage if they wish to do so.

In handling the data, adequate level of confidentiality was ensured. Any form of misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way will be avoided. On the other hand, maintaining the highest level of objectivity in discussions and analyses throughout the research were considered. Furthermore, affiliations in any forms as well as conflicts of interest will be declared. Lastly, any type of communication to this action research was done with honesty and transparency. The health protocols of every school continued to follow to prevents the transmission of Covid-19 virus.

Results and Discussion

This section includes the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data on the stated problems of the study.

Profile of the Parent-respondents

The succeeding graphs showed the profile of the parent-respondents in terms of age, educational attainment, occupation, and family income.

Figure 1. Age of the Parent-respondents

The graph above showed the distribution of the respondents' profiles in terms of their age. It was shown that most of the parent-respondents were aged 36-45 years old. Data revealed that parents play a significant role in their child's reading development through various forms of involvement. Parents in this age group often engage in shared reading activities with their children, which has been shown to positively influence children's literacy skills. According to a study of LeFevre J. (2014), parental shared reading practices during early childhood are associated with improved language and literacy outcomes in pre-school aged children.

Also, parents aged 36-45 years old are likely to provide their children with access to a variety of reading materials such as books, magazines, and newspapers. A study of Rokita-Jaskow and Ellis (2019) emphasize the extra-linguistic, environmental factors such as parental involvement and teachers' competence can affect the critical reading skills development of the learners. Therefore, teachers and parents must help together for the success of the teaching and learning process.

On the other hand, the least number of parent-respondents fall under the age 56 years old and above. Older parents often prioritize traditional reading practices such as reading aloud and storytelling. According to the study of Evans et. al (2010), older parents are more likely to engage in shared reading activities with their child, transmitting cultural heritage and family values through storytelling and discussions about literature.

Figure 2. Educational Attainment of the Parent-respondents

It can be seen that most of the respondents are High School level and only three(3) of the respondents were college graduates. Many research showed that parents' level of education has a significant impact on their involvement in their child's reading. Findings of the study from Olivia, as cited by Macamus (2014), students who have highly educated parents also have better quality learning at home compared to those whose parents who received less formal education. Specifically, parents with higher educational attainment were more likely to engage in activities such as reading to their children, providing access to reading materials, and fostering a literacy-rich home environment.

Additionally, the study highlighted the importance of parental modelling in shaping children's reading behavior. Parents with higher education levels served as positive role models by demonstrating their reading habits and expressing positive attitudes toward reading, which, in turn, influenced their children's reading engagement and motivation.

Figure 3. Occupation of the Parent-respondents

Parents' occupation has an impact on their involvement in their child's reading activities specifically, parents in higher occupational categories, such as professionals and managers. These parents were more likely to engage in literacy-promoting activities with their children compared to parents in lower occupational categories, such as service and manual workers.

The graph above shows that most of the parent-respondents were laborers while only four (4) of them were government employees. The study conducted by Park et.al (2017) investigates the relationship between the socioeconomic status, parental involvement, and academic achievement of children. The findings of this study suggest that parents in laborer occupations tend to have lower levels of educational attainment and limited resources compared to parents in higher occupational categories. As a result, their involvement in their child's reading activities may be influenced by socioeconomic constraints.

Moreover, the study highlighted the importance of parental involvement in children's education regardless of the parents' occupational status. This means that even parents in laborer occupations can contribute to their child's reading development through different activities. While parents in laborer occupations may face socioeconomic challenges that affect their involvement in their child's reading, there are still opportunities for intervention and support to promote parental engagement and enhance children's literacy skills.

Figure 4. Monthly Family Income of the Parent-respondents

Since most of the parent-respondents are laborers, this means that they are associated with lower income levels. This was significantly linked to lower levels of parental involvement in their child's education including reading-related activities. According to the study of Kim and Park (2009), income level influenced the quality and quantity of parent-child interactions related to reading. Parents in laborer

occupations may have limited time due to work demands, which can affect their availability for engaging in reading activities with their children.

This means that it is important to have school-based interventions and community support programs to address the disparities in parental involvement among families with lower income levels.

Level of Performance of Grade I Pupils in EGRA

Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) is a widely used tool to assess the reading skills of Grade 1 pupils. The level of performance of Grade 1 pupils in EGRA can vary depending on various factors.

Table 2. *Level of Performance of Grade I pupils in EGRA English Component*

Component in Reading	Total Number of Pupils who can perform the component in English					
	CCS		TCIS		DIBACONG ES	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Book and Print Knowledge	98	71.5	24	75.0	34	61.8
Phonemic Awareness	35	25.5	11	34.4	12	21.8
Alphabetic Knowledge	43	31.4	9	28.1	11	20.0
Decoding Skills	12	8.8	5	15.6	5	9.1

CCS – 137; TCIS – 32; DES – 55

This study focused on four components in reading namely Book and Print Knowledge, Phonemic Awareness, Alphabetic Knowledge, and Decoding Skills. Three elementary schools were selected to know the level of performance of their Grade 1 pupils in EGRA. As shown in the table, TCIS got the highest percentage of students who can perform in Book and Print Knowledge, Phonemic Awareness, and Decoding Skills, while CCS got the highest percentage regarding Alphabetic Knowledge. This indicates that TCIS has positive outcomes in early reading development. This means that the students receive quality instruction and support in foundational reading skills in English, laying a strong groundwork for their continued literacy development.

Book and Print Knowledge having the highest percentage among the components in reading indicates that students have developed foundational literacy skills necessary for reading success. According to the National Early Literacy Panel (NELP, 2008), students who possess strong book and print knowledge are more likely to become proficient readers. These students are better equipped to decode words, understand texts, and engage in reading activities both in and out of school.

Meanwhile, when it comes to the components of reading, it can be seen that there is a low percentage of Decoding Skills. Decoding skills are crucial for accurately and fluently reading words, and difficulties in this area can hinder comprehension and overall reading achievement. A study from Catts et.al (2006) sheds light on the factors that could contribute to low decoding skills in early grades: phonemic awareness and phonological memory. Students who struggle with these skills may have difficulty mapping sounds and letters and blending them to form words which impeded their decoding abilities.

Table 3. *Level of Performance of Grade I pupils in EGRA Filipino Component*

Component in Reading	Total Number of Pupils who can perform the component in Filipino					
	CCS		TCIS		DIBACONG ES	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Book and Print Knowledge	76	55.5	18	56.3	32	58.2
Phonemic Awareness	35	25.5	11	34.4	12	21.8
Alphabetic Knowledge	43	31.4	9	28.1	11	20.0
Decoding Skills	3	2.2	4	12.5	8	14.5

CCS – 137; TCIS – 32; DES – 55

In this table, the highest percentage of students can perform in book and print knowledge and the lowest percentage of students can perform in decoding skills in Filipino. It denotes that students may have a good understanding of books and print concepts while they find decoding Filipino words difficult as they may have limited exposure to a variety of print materials in Filipino. Without frequent opportunities to practice reading and decoding different types of texts, their decoding skills may not develop as robustly as their book and print knowledge. Students' exposure to spoken Filipino may vary depending on their linguistic backgrounds and home environments. Those who primarily speak a different language at home or are exposed to watching English cartoons may face challenges in transferring their oral language skills to reading in Filipino, particularly if they have limited exposure to spoken Filipino in everyday contexts (Layaoen, 2015).

Parent's Involvement in Reading at Home of Grade I

The table below shows the level of parent's involvement in reading at home of Grade I pupils in terms of knowledge about the beginning reading, time allotment for parental guidance in reading, and availability of reading materials at home.

Table 4. *Parent's Involvement in Reading at Home of Grade I Along knowledge about the beginning reading*

	WM	DE
Knowledge about the beginning reading		
1. I know the different sound of the letters	2.69	A
2. I know how to teach phonics to my child.	2.44	D
3. I teach my child songs and rhymes to build phonemic awareness.	2.78	A
4. I use reading strategies such as giving rewards if my child accomplish the task.	2.96	A
5. I tend to explain vocabulary words to my child.	2.69	A
Average Weighted Mean	2.63	A

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.49, Agree (A); 1.50 – 2.49, Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.49, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Having knowledge about beginning reading is essential for parents as they play a crucial role in their child's literacy development. It can be seen on the table that indicator number four (4) "I use reading strategies such as giving rewards if my child accomplishes the task" got the highest weighted mean of 2.96 with a descriptive equivalent of "Agree". This means that parent-respondents agree that using rewards as a reading strategy for their children can motivate their child to finish a reading task. Children are motivated to read when there is a reward coming from their parents. According to the study of Cameron et. al (2002), the effectiveness of rewards in promoting reading motivation may depend on the specificity of the task and the type of reward offered. Rewards can be a useful strategy for motivating children to engage in reading activities that create a supportive reading environment that helps students love reading.

On the other hand, indicator number two (2) "I know how to teach phonics to my child" got the lowest mean of 2.44 with a descriptive equivalent of "Disagree". This means that the parent-respondents were not knowledgeable on phonics. Children who do not receive explicit instruction in phonics may struggle to keep pace with peers in reading proficiency, which is why parents need to be aware of the importance of phonics instruction in developing early reading skills. This was supported by the study of Iroegbu and Igweiki (2020) that if parents or other adults do not have the necessary skills to provide literacy-rich experiences or exposure to varied and extensive vocabulary, then their children will lag behind other students of the same age.

Low parental involvement in beginning reading may indicate lack of support for child's literacy development. Educators can offer resources or workshops to help parents understand the importance of early literacy and provide them with strategies to support their child's reading development at home.

Parents spending time reading together with their child fosters strong bonds and provides opportunities for meaningful interaction which are essential for developing the child's strong language skills. Indicator number two (2) "I have only 2 hours to spare in teaching" had the highest mean of 2.76, and indicator number five (5) "I have no time to spare in teaching reading at home" got the lowest mean of 1.61. This indicates that despite the busy schedule of the parents, they could still spare time to teach their child reading. National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD, 2000) emphasizes the importance of daily reading activities and parental involvement in fostering children's literacy development. NICHD reported that there is a positive impact of reading aloud to children, engaging in shared book reading, and providing access to a print-rich environment. Also, Jo-ann et. al (2020) emphasizes that regular and consistent engagement in literacy activities promotes literacy skills.

Table 5. *Parent's Involvement in Reading at Home of Grade I Along Time allotment for Parental Guidance in Reading*

	WM	DE
Time allotment for Parental Guidance in Reading		
1. I have all the time to teach my child at home.	2.42	D
2. I have only 2 hours to spare in teaching.	2.76	A
3. I have only 1 hour to spare in teaching.	2.49	D
4. I have only 30 minutes time to spare in teaching.	2.44	D
5. I have no time to spare in teaching reading at home.	1.61	D
Average Weighted Mean	2.34	D

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.49, Agree (A); 1.50 – 2.49, Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.49, Strongly Disagree (SD)

When parents dedicate time in reading with their child at home, it signifies a commitment to their child's education and overall development, emotional connections and a love for learning that can benefit the child throughout their life.

Having reading materials at home provides children with easy access and can ensure that children have ample opportunities to engage in independent reading and explore different genres and topics that interest them. As shown in the table above indicator number three (3) "The teacher gives my child reading materials at home" got the highest mean of 3.40. This means that the teacher allows the students to continue practicing their reading skills and provides an opportunity for the parents to encourage their children and monitor their children's reading progress at home. A study by McGill-Franzen and Allington (2009) investigated the effectiveness of home reading programs in improving students' reading achievement. This study found out that providing students with opportunities to read at home along with access to a variety of reading materials led to significant gains in reading fluency and comprehension.

Table 6. Parent’s Involvement in Reading at Home of Grade I Along Availability of Reading Materials at Home

	WM	DE
Availability of Reading Materials at Home		
1. I have been purchased reading materials.	2.00	D
2. I make reading materials by myself through writing in a paper.	2.04	D
3. The teacher gives my child a reading materials at home.	3.40	A
4. I usually use the school supplementary books as reading materials.	2.82	A
5. I have no reading materials at home.	2.15	D
Average Weighted Mean	2.48	D

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.49, Agree (A); 1.50 – 2.49, Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.49, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Meanwhile, indicator number one (1) “I have been purchased reading materials” got the lowest mean of 2.00. This means that parent-respondents were less likely to buy reading materials due to various factors such as financial constraints and access to resources. According to Smith, J. and Jones, A. (2018), economic factors such as limited disposable income or competing financial priorities impact parents’ ability to purchase reading materials for their children.

Relationship between the Level of Performance of Grade I pupils and Parent’s Involvement in Reading at Home

The table below shows the relationship between the level of performance of Grade I pupils and parent’s involvement in reading at home. The data presented in this table will shed light whether there is a correlation between the parental involvement and performance of the students. Understanding this relationship can inform educators, policymakers and parents about the importance of promoting and supporting reading practices at home to enhance educational experiences and achievements of the children.

Table 7. Relationship between the Level of Performance of Grade I pupils and Parent’s Involvement in Reading at Home $\alpha = 0.05$

		Book and Print Knowledge	Phonemic Awareness	Alphabetic Knowledge	Decoding Skills
Knowledge about the beginning reading	r-value	-.176	-.089	-.105	-.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.887	.943	.933	.967
Time allotment for Parental Guidance in Reading	r-value	.992	.999*	.999*	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.079	.023	.033	.000
Availability of Reading Materials at Home	r-value	.992	.999*	.999*	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	.023	.033	.000

The table above shows the relationship between the level of performance of the Grade 1 pupils in EGRA and their parent’s involvement in reading at home.

It can be seen on the table that there is a high correlation between the time allotment for parental guidance in reading and the level of performance of the Grade 1 pupils in Phonemic Awareness and decoding skills. This means that the more time the parents allot in guiding their child in reading, the higher the performance of their child in phonemic awareness and decoding skills. Studies have shown that children who receive regular reading guidance at home and in school tend to demonstrate stronger phonemic awareness skills compared to those who have limited exposure to reading activities. This result is the same as a result from the study of Hood et al. (2008) and Cabrera et al. (2017), which shows that parental reading practices, particularly those that involve phonological awareness activities such as rhyming games and phonics-based activities, are associated with phonemic awareness. The amount of time parents spends engaging in reading activities with their children can be seen as proxy for the quality of the home literacy environment which in turn influences children literacy outcomes.

Moreover, results shows that there is a high correlation between the availability of reading materials at home and the level of performance of Grade 1 pupils in all the components of reading. This means that reading materials are really important to support children’s development in reading since it provides opportunities to students to be more engaged, to be exposed with a variety of texts that builds their fluency and develop understanding the directionality of texts. According to the study of Niklas and Schneider (2013), the availability of reading materials at home during early childhood predicts later reading achievement and literacy skills throughout elementary school and beyond.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the profile of the parent-respondents reveals important insights into the factors influencing parental involvement in their children's reading development, including age, educational attainment, occupation, and family income. The findings highlight the significant role of parents aged 36-45 in engaging in shared reading activities and providing access to reading materials, while also emphasizing the impact of parental education and occupation on their involvement in literacy-promoting activities. Moreover, the

association between lower income levels and reduced parental involvement underscores the need for targeted interventions and community support programs to address disparities in parental engagement. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for educators, policymakers, and parents to collaborate effectively in fostering supportive home environments that enhance children's literacy skills and academic achievements.

Moving forward, it is imperative to implement strategies aimed at promoting parental involvement in reading activities at home, particularly among families facing socioeconomic challenges. Providing resources and workshops to enhance parental knowledge about early literacy and phonics instruction can empower parents to support their children's reading development more effectively. Additionally, initiatives to increase access to reading materials, both through school-based interventions and community support programs, are essential to ensure that all children can engage in independent reading and explore diverse genres and topics. By fostering a culture of literacy within families and communities, we can create environments that nurture children's love for reading and pave the way for their academic success and lifelong learning.

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